

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	Timepix3 detector calibration and characterization with proton beams
Project TA identifier	TA09-276
General application	High-energy accelerators
Type of test	Radiation monitor calibration
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Date(s) of the experiment	2024, February, 24-26
Facility	Centro Nacional de Aceleradores (CNA)
Amount of access granted	24 h

Objectives of the experiments

Following a previous test campaign partly published in [1] and reported in [2], this project aimed at investigating the per pixel energy deposition and calibration of the Timepix3 Radiation Monitor used within the Radiation to Electronics (R2E) group at CERN.

The main objective is to quantify the saturation threshold of the detector, assumed at 600 keV/pixel. Higher energy depositions spoil the calibration, requiring more sophisticated charge reconstruction algorithms that take into account non-linearities above this estimated saturation threshold. As side objectives, the test campaign will be beneficial for optimization of both online and offline data processing for the detector software, as well as to study the charge transport mechanisms of the deposited charge results in charge sharing amongst pixels (formation of pixel clusters). For this, the CNA TANDEM facility providing protons in range of 600 to 2100 keV was used.

A second objective is to experimentally measure the depletion layer, using a fully penetrating beam in the of Minimum Ionising Particle (MIP) and irradiation at several angles to determine the depth of the depletion layer. For this, the CNA compact cyclotron was used, providing protons at 14.8 MeV. Moreover, this data can also be used to improve the algorithms computing the angle of irradiation for arbitrary data.

[1] D. Prelipcean et al. "Towards a Timepix3 Radiation Monitor for the Accelerator Mixed Radiation Field: Characterisation with Protons and Alphas from 0.6 MeV to 5.6 MeV". In: Applied Sciences 14.2 (2024). ISSN: 2076-3417. DOI: 10.3390/app14020624.

[2] D. Prelipcean. "Timepix3 radiation monitor at CNA - mono-energetic proton (alpha) beams ranging from 0.6 (1) to 5 (8.4) MeV". EDMS document 3163127

<https://radnext.web.cern.ch/>

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Experiment test report

1. Description of the experimental setup

In the first part of the campaign, according to the initial considerations, the Timepix3 detector module was installed in the vacuum chamber, which was the only part of the system inside the vacuum chamber, as shown in Fig. 1. The detector was previously irradiated while operated at a bias voltage of 50 V [1, 2], leading to a partial depletion layer. For this test campaign, the detector was operated at a bias voltage of 80 V, leading to a full depletion.

Fig. 1: Timepix3 setup layout diagram.

In the second part of the campaign, the detector was mounted at the compact cyclotron facility, as shown in Fig 2. It consists of one beamline capable to provide higher energy protons compared to the TANDEM. The Timepix3 Radiation Monitor was installed about 54 cm from the end of the vacuumed beamline, meaning that the protons will be slightly attenuated in air from the nominal compact cyclotron energy. It is estimated that the protons arriving on the sensor have an energy of $E_{\text{proton}}=14.8$ MeV.

The detector has been mounted on a rotating table. Initially, the plan was to automatically/remotely rotate the table, without requiring human access. However, the weight of the Timepix3 detector modules and the extra pull from the ethernet cables rendered it impractical/impossible for the rotating table to be operated because of the excess weight. Therefore, human access was needed to rotate the detector at each angle, implying a downtime of about 10 minutes for each data point.

Due to the pile-up uncertainty, the lowest possible fluxes were requested. Retrospectively, the largest beam flux recorded at CNA was in the order of 10^7 particles/(cm^2 s), at least one order of magnitude lower than the theoretical limit computed for physical pileup based on the detector timing resolution. Therefore, one does not expect physical pile-ups to be a significant issue, but the bottleneck is the clustering algorithm.

2. Event selection and cluster parameters

The first step of the analysis of data from the Timepix3 Radiation Monitor irradiations is the pixel clustering procedure, aimed at identifying the single-particle hits. Before the calibration can be carried out, it is beneficial to define a cluster filtering method to ensure that the clusters from single-particle hits

are fully reconstructed and isolated protons, hence removing partially reconstructed clusters and/or pileup events from the analysis. The filtering approach used here relies on using the mono-chromaticity of the proton beam. One identifies the main Gaussian peak in the ToT distribution, as shown in Fig. 3, and preserves only the clusters with a ToT within $1\text{-}\sigma$. Similarly, the fitting can be applied on the cluster sizes.

Fig. 2: Timepix3 Radiation Monitor installed at the CNA compact cyclotron.

Fig. 3: Example of the Timepix3 Radiation Monitor measurements for a proton run at 794 keV, displaying (Left) the total ToT per cluster and (Right) the cluster size (number of pixels).

3. Calibration at 80 V bias voltage

The cluster ToT volume data presented above serve as the basis for the Timepix3 Radiation Monitor calibration, obtained via the procedure outlined in Ref. [1]. Along with the ToT data, FLUKA simulations are employed to quantify the energy deposited E_{dep} in the sensor from a beam of particles E_0 , such that one takes into account the energy lost in the aluminum metalization layer, with a known thickness of 500 nm, and in the dead layer, with a thickness estimated at 330 nm, along with the measured average ToT and number of pixels per cluster N for each energy.

Fig. 4: Calibration of the Timepix3 Radiation Monitor, fully biased at 80 V.

The cluster-level calibration is obtained by plotting the mean values of the cluster ToT (obtained by fitting the ToT curves, as shown exemplarily in Fig. 3) as a function of the corresponding deposited energies in the active volume of the sensor as illustrated in Fig. 4. No saturation effects are assumed, yielding a linear calibration fit as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 ToT_{reg}(E_{dep}) = & E_{dep} \cdot \left[572 \pm 80(\sigma_{ToT}) \pm 36(\sigma_E) \pm 36(\sigma_{fit}) \right] \left[\frac{25 \text{ ns}}{\text{MeV}} \right] \\
 & + N \cdot \left[56.2 \pm 3.5(\sigma_{fit}) \pm 1.0(\sigma_{ToT}) \pm 0.4(\sigma_E) \right] \left[\frac{25 \text{ ns}}{\text{pixel}} \right] \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

where the variable cluster size N is considered. The uncertainties are as follows: σ_{ToT} is the averaged 1- σ of the measured ToT values per cluster for all the beam energies, σ_E is the beam energy uncertainty, evaluated at an average of 3% over all beam energies as communicated by the facility, and $\sigma_{fit} = 6.2\%$

is the error on the least squares fit of the calibration curve.

4. Irradiation at an angle

The detector was also irradiated with higher-energy protons that penetrate fully the detector. The (polar) angle of incidence θ on the Timepix3 array has been computed assuming a depth of $W = 300 \mu\text{m}$ and a transversal elongation equal to the 2D length of the cluster track. Since the pixel could have been hit on either edge (e.g. left or right), there is an uncertainty of at least one pixel width, leading to an angular range as $[\theta_{\min}, \theta_{\max}]$, and a weight of $w = 1/(\theta_{\max} - \theta_{\min})$ is assigned for the corresponding bins within the angular range. This leads to the results shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Timepix3 reconstructed polar angle θ at the CNA proton compact cyclotron, showing also the setup irradiation angle (vertical dashed gray lines).

To conclude, the campaign was successful in completing all its proposed objectives.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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